

Career Guidance Under Constraint: Practitioner perspectives on time, capacity and delivery conditions

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About this working paper

This working paper presents findings from practitioner-led research into time, capacity and delivery conditions within career guidance practice.

It is being published independently to support professional discussion, practitioner reflection and further research into the conditions that shape the quality and accessibility of career guidance.

The paper has not yet undergone formal academic peer review. It should therefore be read as a practitioner-led contribution to an emerging evidence base rather than as a definitive or representative account of the career development profession as a whole.

The findings and interpretations presented are those of the author. Any future revisions, responses to feedback or peer-reviewed versions will be clearly identified through updated version information.

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Abstract

Career guidance is widely recognised as a key mechanism for supporting progression, employability and social mobility. However, limited attention has been given to the conditions under which guidance is delivered, particularly practitioner capacity, time allocation and administrative workload.

This study presents findings from a survey of 296 career development professionals, primarily working in secondary schools and colleges. It examines daily appointment numbers, appointment length, administrative demands and perceived capacity constraints. Results indicate a mixed model of delivery, with a substantial proportion of practitioners operating below a 45-minute session. The data also indicates that shorter appointments are frequently embedded rather than occasional. Administrative workload, particularly action planning and reporting, emerges as a significant demand on practitioner time, often extending beyond contracted hours. Respondents also report increasing involvement in wider programme responsibilities, further limiting available capacity.

When considered alongside existing evidence from secondary, higher education and adult guidance contexts, a consistent pattern emerges. Although the specific pressures and delivery structures vary across settings, similar challenges relating to practitioner time, administrative workload and appointment structures are evident. Across contexts, capacity constraints are associated with shorter appointments, increased administrative burden and more transactional interactions. This evidence suggests that guidance effectiveness is time-sensitive, with reduced interaction time limiting depth, personalisation and follow-up support.

The study highlights a gap in system-level measurement of key delivery conditions, including appointment length, appointment volume, caseload, administrative time and follow-up capacity. It argues that these factors should be understood as core inputs into effective guidance practice and better reflected in evaluation frameworks, particularly where learners face additional barriers or require proportional support for more complex needs.

1. Introduction

Career guidance has long occupied an important place within education, employability, skills, industrial and social mobility policy at both national and international levels (Herr, 2001; Mulvey, 2006). Across secondary, further and higher education, as well as adult employment support services, it is expected to help individuals make informed decisions, develop career readiness and progress towards positive destinations. Moreover, return-on-investment analysis suggests that for every £1 invested in career guidance, the country can expect a return of approximately £2.50 for youth guidance and £3.20 for guidance with unemployed adults (Hooley, Percy and Neary, 2023).

Alongside research exploring outcomes, recent work has also examined the wider enablers of successful career development, emphasising the importance of contextual and structural

factors that shape career trajectories and opportunities (Franklin and Ayentimi, 2025). However, comparatively less attention has been given to the delivery conditions under which career guidance itself is provided. There are increasing indications across both research and practice that career guidance delivery is becoming more constrained, particularly in relation to practitioner capacity, appointment time and administrative workload. Emerging evidence from higher education and adult guidance services suggests that:

- Appointment lengths are being reduced in response to increased demand
- Practitioner workloads are shaped by high caseloads and administrative requirements
- Time available for in-depth, individualised guidance may be limited

At the same time, policy and evaluation frameworks tend to focus primarily on outcomes, such as participation, progression and destinations, with comparatively limited attention given to the delivery conditions that underpin guidance practice.

This creates a potential gap in understanding:

‘To what extent are current delivery models aligned with the conditions required for effective career guidance?’

1.1 Study focus and rationale

This study seeks to contribute to this question by examining practitioner experience and perspectives on:

- Appointment volume, length and structure
- Administrative workload
- Perceived capacity constraints

Drawing on survey data from career development professionals across multiple settings (predominantly secondary schools and colleges) this research provides an empirical snapshot of how guidance is currently experienced at the point of delivery.

While the sample is weighted toward school-based provision, the findings are considered alongside existing research from higher education and adult guidance contexts to explore whether similar patterns are evident across the wider sector.

1.2 Framing the contribution

As research examining delivery conditions within career guidance remains comparatively limited, this study takes an exploratory approach to investigate practitioner perspectives on capacity, appointment structures and administrative workload. Therefore, the purpose of this study is not to test a predefined hypothesis, but rather to:

- Identify recurring patterns in practitioner experience
- Situate these patterns within the broader evidence base
- Explore their implications for service design and system understanding

In particular, the study highlights the role of time as a central organising factor in guidance delivery and raises questions about how practitioner capacity is currently distributed and how administrative demands interact with client-facing work. Moreover, it examines whether key aspects of delivery (e.g. appointment length, caseload and administrative time) are sufficiently visible at system level.

1.3 Structure of the paper

The paper is structured as follows:

- Section 2 outlines the methodology and survey design
- Section 3 presents the findings from the practitioner survey
- Section 4 provides contextual evidence from existing research across secondary education, higher education and adult guidance contexts
- Section 5 integrates these findings to identify common themes and system-level patterns
- Section 6 sets out implications and recommendations at practitioner, organisational and system levels

2. Methodology

2.1 Research design

This study adopts an online, cross-sectional survey design to explore how career guidance is currently delivered from a practitioner perspective, with a particular focus on appointment number, length, administrative workload and perceived capacity constraints.

The survey was designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative insights into practitioner experience. It included a combination of closed questions (e.g. appointment length, frequency of shorter sessions, time allocation) and open-text responses, allowing participants to describe in more detail the factors influencing their day-to-day practice.

The combination of structured quantitative questions and open-text responses enables the identification of both measurable patterns and recurring qualitative themes.

2.2 Sample and participants

A total of **296 responses** were collected from career development professionals working across a range of settings, with a strong representation from school-based provision.

The sample includes:

- Secondary schools with sixth form (11–18): 36.1% (n=107)
- Secondary schools (11–16): 19.6% (n=58)
- Further education colleges: 10.8% (n=32)
- Higher education careers services: 9.8% (n=29)

Additional responses were drawn from sixth form colleges, local authority services, private and independent practitioners as well as third-sector provision. The majority of respondents were directly involved in guidance delivery, with 58.4% (n=173) identifying as careers advisers. This indicates that the findings largely reflect the experiences of frontline practitioners.

2.3 Data collection

The survey was distributed through professional networks and practitioner communities, including online platforms and direct contacts. Data collection took place over a 67-day period, allowing for a broad range of responses across different settings.

Participants were asked to reflect on their typical working patterns and where relevant, their experience within the previous four weeks. This approach was intended to capture current delivery conditions while limiting reliance on long-term recall.

2.4 Analytical approach

Quantitative data from closed questions were analysed using descriptive statistical methods, focusing on frequency distributions and proportional analysis. This allowed for identification of key patterns, including appointment length, frequency of shortened sessions and indicators of workload pressure.

Qualitative responses were analysed using a thematic coding approach, whereby responses were reviewed and grouped into recurring themes based on frequency and conceptual similarity. Key themes included administrative workload, appointment structure, resourcing and staffing, as well as competing responsibilities within the wider careers programme.

2.5 Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings. Firstly, the sample is weighted toward school-based provision, meaning that findings may be more representative of secondary education contexts than of further education, higher education or adult services.

Secondly, the study is based on voluntary participation and was distributed through professional networks and practitioner communities. As such, the sample may be subject to self-selection bias, with practitioners experiencing capacity pressures, workload concerns or strong views about delivery conditions potentially more likely to respond. This means that the findings should not be interpreted as a nationally representative measure of prevalence or sentiment across the whole career development workforce.

Thirdly, the study relies on self-reported data, which may be influenced by individual perception, role context and variation in how respondents interpret terms such as “guidance appointment”, “administrative workload” or “capacity pressure”. The survey should therefore be understood as practitioner-level evidence of perceived delivery conditions, rather than as an objective audit of provision.

These limitations do not remove the value of the findings. Rather, the consistency of themes across responses and their alignment with existing research, provides evidence of some concerning and important dynamics within current guidance delivery. In particular, the findings suggest that appointment length, administrative workload, caseload pressure and follow-up capacity warrant greater attention in future research and system-level monitoring.

Finally, the study is descriptive rather than causal. It does not seek to establish direct relationships between variables, but rather to identify patterns in how guidance delivery is experienced under current conditions. As an exploratory study, these findings should not be interpreted as establishing causal relationships between delivery conditions and outcomes.

However, it is hoped that this foundational research will provide a basis for future studies that test hypotheses and examine the strength of relationships between delivery conditions, resource allocation and guidance outcomes at scale. Future research could also examine learner perceptions of appointment length, quality and sufficiency, including how students and clients experience different guidance formats and whether shorter, longer or repeated appointments are perceived as being appropriate to their needs.

3. Findings

3.1 Appointment structures and duration

The survey data indicates a range of appointment lengths across settings, with a notable spread between shorter and longer guidance sessions. As shown in Table 1, the most commonly reported appointment duration was 40–45 minutes, selected by 37.5% of respondents. However, 26.4% reported delivering 30-minute appointments, while smaller proportions reported 20-minute appointments or mixed/variable models.

Table 1: Reported standard appointment duration

Appointment duration	n	%
40–45 minutes	111	37.5%
30 minutes	78	26.4%
50–60 minutes	68	23.0%
Varies widely / mixed model	19	6.4%
Not applicable	8	2.7%
20 minutes	7	2.4%
60+ minutes	5	1.7%
Total	296	100.0%

Note. Survey question: “What appointment lengths do you typically deliver for 1:1 guidance?” Percentages are calculated from the full survey sample (n=296), including respondents for whom the question was not applicable, and may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Overall, while the largest proportion of respondents reported delivering sessions in the 40–45-minute range, a substantial minority reported shorter standard appointment lengths, particularly 30-minute sessions. This indicates that while a longer session model remains present, shorter appointment structures are widely embedded within current delivery models.

3.2 Variability and shortening of appointments

In addition to standard appointment number and length, respondents were asked about the frequency with which shorter appointments (30 minutes or less) had been delivered in the previous four weeks.

Findings indicate that 17.6% of respondents reported that 30-minute or shorter appointments occurred “almost always” (90%+). A further proportion reported that such appointments occurred frequently (e.g. more than half of sessions). This demonstrates that for a significant subset of practitioners, shortened appointments are not occasional adaptations but form a dominant part of delivery.

Qualitative responses indicate that shorter appointment lengths are often linked to:

- High demand and waiting lists
- Timetabling constraints
- Pressure to increase throughput

Taken together, the data implies that the use of shorter appointment formats reflects a broader pattern of time compression within guidance delivery.

3.3 Appointment volume and daily workload

Survey responses indicate that the number of one-to-one guidance appointments delivered per day varies across practitioners. The most frequently reported appointment volume was 5–6 clients per day (38.9%, n=115), followed by 3–4 clients per day (24.0%, n=71). This is notable when considered alongside DfE statutory guidance, which states that the CDI recommends at least 45 minutes for every personal guidance meeting (Department for Education, 2025). Moreover, in a publication for The Careers & Enterprise Company, Percy’s ROI modelling uses a midpoint delivery assumption of six interviews per day, each lasting 45 minutes plus preparation and follow-up (Percy, 2020). While Percy’s model should not be interpreted as a formal workload standard, it provides a useful sector-based comparator for considering daily appointment volume.

A notable minority reported higher appointment volumes. Specifically, 16.9% (n=50) reported delivering 7–8 appointments per day, while 7.4% (n=22) reported 9–10 appointments. Smaller proportions reported delivering 11–12 appointments (1.0%, n=3) or 13 or more appointments (1.4%, n=4). This indicates that over one quarter of respondents reported delivering seven or more appointments per day, and approximately one in ten reported delivering nine or more. When considered alongside findings on appointment length and administrative workload, this suggests that shorter appointment formats may, in some contexts, reflect an attempt to accommodate higher daily appointment volumes within constrained working hours. The full distribution of reported daily appointment volume is shown in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Number of guidance appointments delivered per day

Appointments per day	n	%
0–2	24	8.1%
3–4	71	24.0%
5–6	115	38.9%
7–8	50	16.9%
9–10	22	7.4%
11–12	3	1.0%
13+	4	1.4%
Not applicable	7	2.4%

Note. Survey question: “How many 1:1 guidance appointments do you typically deliver in a day?” Percentages are calculated from the full survey sample (n=296) and may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Further exploratory analysis supports this interpretation. Using midpoint estimates for appointment-volume and appointment-duration categories, a statistically significant negative correlation was found between the number of appointments delivered per day and typical appointment length (Spearman’s rho = -0.369, p < .001, n = 269). This indicates that practitioners reporting higher daily appointment volumes tended to report shorter appointment durations. However, as the study is descriptive and based on categorical self-reported data, this association should not be interpreted as causal. The pattern is illustrated below:

Table 3: Appointment volume and estimated appointment duration

Appointments per day	Valid n	Mean estimated appointment duration	% reporting 30 mins or less
0–2	22	46.4 mins	13.6%
3–4	66	43.6 mins	19.7%
5–6	110	44.9 mins	20.0%
7–8	46	36.0 mins	56.5%
9–10	21	30.5 mins	85.7%
11+	4	33.1 mins	75.0%

Note. Based on the survey questions: “How many 1:1 guidance appointments do you typically deliver in a day?” and “What appointment lengths do you typically deliver for 1:1 guidance?” Mean duration was estimated using category midpoints; “varies widely / mixed model” and “not applicable” responses were excluded.

3.4 Administrative workload and time allocation

Administrative workload emerges as a significant component of practitioner time use. Respondents were asked how many hours they spend on guidance-related administration in a typical week. As shown in Table 4, 60.5% reported spending five or more hours per week on guidance-related administration, while 28.4% reported spending eight or more hours and 11.5% reported spending 11 or more hours.

Table 4: Weekly guidance-related administrative time

Weekly guidance-related admin time	n	%
Under 2 hours	31	10.5%
2–4 hours	78	26.4%
5–7 hours	95	32.1%
8–10 hours	50	16.9%
11–15 hours	16	5.4%
16–20 hours	12	4.1%
21+ hours	6	2.0%
Not sure	8	2.7%
Total	296	100.0%

Note. Survey question: “How many hours do you spend on guidance-related administration in a typical week?” Percentages are calculated from the full survey sample (n=296) and may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Respondents were also asked which guidance-related administrative tasks take the most time in their role. As shown in Table 5, action plans and written summaries were the most frequently reported demand, selected by 78.4% of respondents, followed by emails and follow-up contact, as well as case notes or record keeping.

Table 5: Guidance-related administrative tasks reported as taking most time

Administrative task	n	% of respondents
Action plans / written summaries	232	78.4%
Emails and follow-up contact	149	50.3%
Case notes / record keeping	113	38.2%
Scheduling / booking	59	19.9%
Tracking destinations / outcomes	45	15.2%
Referrals / liaison with external agencies	40	13.5%
CRM / data entry systems	33	11.1%
Evidence / reporting requirements, e.g. Gatsby, Ofsted or funders	29	9.8%

Note. Survey question: “Which guidance-related administrative tasks take the most time in your role?” Respondents could select up to three options, so percentages do not sum to 100%.

A consistent theme across responses is that administrative work competes directly with time available for client-facing activity. This admin work is often undertaken outside scheduled appointment time and sometimes contributes to workload extending beyond contracted hours. Moreover, qualitative responses highlight that action planning and documentation are particularly time-intensive and that duplication of data entry across systems is a common issue faced by professionals. Another common theme represented in the qualitative responses is that administrative expectations are not always aligned with available time.

This suggests that capacity constraints are shaped not only by the number of appointments delivered, but by the cumulative administrative workload associated with each interaction.

3.5 Competing responsibilities within the wider careers programme

In addition to appointment delivery and administrative workload, open-text responses indicate that practitioner capacity is also shaped by competing responsibilities beyond one-to-one guidance. A keyword-based analysis of 294 completed open-text responses identified 47 statements (16.0%) that explicitly referred to wider duties. These responses did not represent the dominant theme across the full open-text dataset, where many participants focused on staffing, appointment time, administrative workload and resourcing. However, they indicate that a meaningful minority of practitioners experience capacity pressure because guidance is combined with wider careers programme responsibilities.

Table 6: Wider duties referenced in open-text responses

Theme	n
Wider programme, Gatsby Benchmark or work experience responsibilities	22
Teaching, curriculum or timetable-related duties	19
Events, workshops, assemblies or employer engagement	12

Note. Themes were identified through keyword-based analysis of completed open-text responses. Categories overlap because some responses referred to more than one responsibility.

These findings suggest that capacity pressures are multifaceted and are influenced not only by appointment volume and administrative workload, but also by the expansion of practitioner roles across the wider careers programme.

3.6 Indicators of practitioner capacity pressure

Across both quantitative and qualitative responses, multiple indicators point to sustained pressure on practitioner capacity. Key patterns include:

- Back-to-back appointment schedules, with limited breaks between sessions
- Limited or no protected time for administrative work
- Spillover of work into evenings and weekends
- Delays in completing action plans or follow-up tasks

In response to a multi-select question on drivers of shorter appointments ‘High demand / waiting lists (n=112)’ was the most frequently selected factor alongside ‘Timetabling constraints (n=90)’ which was also widely reported. Moreover, ‘Funding / contract requirements’ (n=34) and ‘Staffing levels / vacancies’ (n=32) were identified as contributing factors.

Table 7: Reported drivers of shorter appointment lengths

Driver of shorter appointment lengths	n
High demand / long waiting lists	112
Timetabling constraints	90
Other	69
Triage model	64
Leadership expectations / targets	60
Client complexity is lower in most cases	48
Funding / contract requirements	34
Staffing levels / vacancies	32
Digital model	17

Note. Survey question: “What most commonly drives shorter appointment lengths in your setting?” Counts do not sum to the total sample because respondents could select up to three options.

These findings suggest that shorter appointments are most commonly associated with immediate operational pressures, particularly high demand, waiting lists and timetabling constraints. However, the range of reported drivers, including triage models, leadership expectations, funding constraints and staffing pressures, signal that appointment shortening is also shaped by wider organisational and structural conditions. While funding and staffing were not the most frequently selected drivers, they remain relevant when considered alongside qualitative responses describing limited capacity and unmet demand. Taken together, these findings imply that practitioner capacity is under sustained pressure, driven by a combination of demand, structural constraints, administrative workload and competing role responsibilities.

3.7 Summary of key findings

Across the dataset, several consistent patterns emerge:

- 1) A mixed model of appointment lengths, with a substantial proportion of practitioners delivering sessions below 45 minutes
- 2) Evidence that shortened appointments are frequently embedded within delivery, rather than used occasionally
- 3) A significant administrative workload, which competes with client-facing time and contributes to workload spillover
- 4) The presence of competing responsibilities beyond guidance, including work experience, events, teaching and wider programme delivery
- 5) Multiple indicators of capacity pressure, including high demand, limited time, and structural constraints

These findings provide a practitioner-level perspective on how career guidance is currently delivered and form the basis for further analysis in relation to wider evidence and system-level implications.

4. Context and Existing Evidence

4.1 Overview of the evidence base

The findings presented in Section 3 raise questions about whether these patterns are specific to the surveyed sample or reflect wider trends across the career guidance sector. Research on career guidance has traditionally focused on outcomes, including progression into education, employment and training, as well as measures of career readiness and decision-making capability.

This outcome-focused evidence is important. A substantial body of research indicates that careers education and guidance can contribute to positive outcomes, including career readiness, sustained destinations, reduced NEET risk and longer-term labour-market benefits (Dodd, Hanson and Hooley, 2021; Percy and Tanner, 2021; Gatsby Charitable Foundation, 2024; Moote et al., 2025). However, evidence that career guidance can be effective does not, in itself show whether practitioners have sufficient time, resourcing and administrative capacity to deliver guidance sustainably and at the depth intended.

Recent DfE analysis of linked longitudinal and administrative data adds further relevance to this question by identifying groups of young people at heightened risk of becoming NEET. The report finds that having an EHCP, persistent absence during KS4 and low GCSE attainment are among the strongest factors associated with later NEET status. It also shows that risk is

cumulative, with young people facing multiple overlapping risk factors requiring a more holistic approach to prevention (Department for Education, 2026). This is significant for career guidance because students with additional barriers may require more sustained, personalised and follow-up support. Evidence from specialist settings also suggests that careers guidance for students with SEND is strongest where it is dedicated and distinct from general transition planning, rather than treated as an incidental or absorbed function (Mintz, 2025).

This wider challenge is reflected in Milburn's (2026) Young People and Work interim report, which argues that youth transitions are shaped by fragmented accountability across education, health, welfare and employment systems and that young people facing overlapping barriers are often least well served by existing support structures. Viewed in this context, understanding guidance capacity becomes not only a workforce issue, but also an equity and progression issue.

This distinction is central to the present study. Positive evidence of impact strengthens the case for understanding the delivery conditions that make effective guidance possible. Yet there remains a comparatively smaller body of work examining these conditions directly, particularly in relation to practitioner capacity, time allocation and administrative workload.

Where these factors are explored, a consistent pattern emerges across settings: guidance delivery is shaped by the availability of time and time itself is constrained by structural and operational pressures.

4.2 Appointment length and guidance effectiveness

Several studies suggest that the length and structure of guidance interactions are closely linked to their depth and effectiveness. Evidence from adult guidance services indicates that higher-quality interactions are associated with longer engagement durations. For example, evaluations of telephone guidance services found that the highest-quality calls were typically within the 30–50-minute range, with no high-quality interactions recorded below 20 minutes (DfES, 2007). Similarly, structured guidance interventions such as Skills Health Checks have historically been designed around approximately 45-minute appointments, allowing sufficient time for diagnostic discussion and action planning (DWP, 2011b).

In the context of higher education, recent research has highlighted the implications of reducing appointment length as a response to demand pressures. Shortened sessions have been associated with a shift toward more focused or transactional interactions, with reduced opportunity for exploration and reflective discussion. This is supported by research indicating that reducing appointment length can constrain the depth and relational nature of guidance interactions (Reid, 2022).

Recent evidence from Stevens (2026) further supports this concern. In a survey of 84 career guidance practitioners, Stevens found wide variation in one-to-one appointment length, with HE practitioners reporting a median and modal appointment length of 30 minutes. The study also found that practitioners offering appointments of 30 minutes or less reported fewer

existential topics in guidance conversations than those also offering longer appointments. This raised questions about whether shorter sessions restrict reflective space or reinforce more transactional approaches.

More broadly, longitudinal research on careers education and guidance argues that greater exposure to guidance and related activities is associated with improved longer-term outcomes, including progression and career satisfaction (Moote et al., 2025). While this research does not isolate appointment length specifically, it reinforces the importance of sufficient time and engagement as part of effective provision.

Collectively, these findings indicate that the effectiveness of guidance is at least in part, time-dependent, with reduced interaction time potentially limiting the scope and depth of support.

4.3 Capacity constraints in adult guidance and employment support services

Research from adult guidance and employment support contexts provides further insight into how capacity constraints shape delivery models. In Jobcentre Plus settings, national audit and parliamentary reports have identified shortfalls in work coach capacity and high caseload. They also detail the use of operational flexibilities such as reducing initial appointment lengths from 50 to 30 minutes in response to workload pressures (National Audit Office, 2025; Committee of Public Accounts, 2025).

Qualitative research within these settings also describes a shift toward more process-driven interactions, where practitioners are required to prioritise compliance, data entry and transactional tasks within limited timeframes (DWP, 2011a). Routine Jobcentre Plus interactions have also been observed to operate within very short timeframes, with some work search reviews lasting around 10 minutes, limiting the scope of engagement (DWP, 2025). Similarly, studies of Universal Credit implementation highlight how digital systems and administrative requirements can generate continuous, fragmented workloads, reducing the time available for meaningful client engagement (Dwyer et al., 2025).

Beyond statutory services, third-sector employability programmes report comparable dynamics. Practitioners frequently describe administrative tasks such as reporting, evidence collection and follow-up as consuming a significant proportion of working time, in some cases approaching parity with client-facing activity (Irvine et al., 2023).

4.4 Administrative burden and the distribution of practitioner time

Across the evidence base, administrative workload emerges not simply as an additional task, but as a competing demand on practitioner time. These administrative requirements included session documentation and action planning, data entry and case management systems, as well as reporting for funding or compliance purposes.

Multiple studies show that these activities can reduce the time available for client interaction, contribute to time pressure within appointments and extend workload beyond scheduled hours (Irvine et al., 2023; Dwyer et al., 2025; DWP, 2011a).

This further reinforces the interpretation that capacity constraints are shaped not only by the number of clients seen, but by how practitioner time is allocated across different functions.

4.5 A gap in measurement and system visibility

Despite the consistency of these findings, there remains a notable gap in how career guidance systems are understood and evaluated. While outcome measures are relatively well developed, there is limited standardised data across the sector on key delivery conditions such as appointment volume, appointment duration and variation in delivery patterns. Other factors lacking consistent measurement include practitioner caseload size and time spent on administrative tasks. As a result, it is difficult to assess whether guidance is being delivered under conditions that support effective practice. It also makes it challenging to compare delivery models across settings and/or to identify where capacity constraints are most acute. This measurement gap is also reflected in recent work describing one-to-one career guidance as a “black box”, where limited empirical attention has been given to the content, structure and processes of guidance conversations themselves (Stevens, 2026). This lack of visibility is particularly significant because time appears to function as a central organising variable in guidance delivery, shaping both practitioner activity and the potential depth of support provided.

4.6 Positioning this study

In this context, the present study contributes practitioner-level evidence on:

- How time is experienced and allocated in practice
- How administrative demands interact with delivery
- How capacity pressures are perceived across settings

By combining these insights with existing research from secondary education, higher education and adult guidance contexts, this study seeks to bridge the gap between practitioner experience and system-level understanding of guidance delivery conditions.

5. Integrated Discussion

When considered alongside evidence from secondary, higher education and adult guidance contexts, the findings from this study point to a consistent pattern: career guidance delivery is increasingly shaped by capacity constraints, with time functioning as a central limitation within practice. This matters because the wider evidence base shows that careers guidance

can contribute to positive outcomes for young people, schools and wider society, including improved career readiness, progression and longer-term labour-market outcomes (Dodd, Hanson and Hooley, 2021; Percy and Tanner, 2021; Moote et al., 2025; Percy and Hooley, 2024).

The question raised by this study is therefore not whether guidance is valuable, but whether current delivery conditions are sufficiently visible and sustainable to support the depth and quality of practice that effective guidance requires. Across settings, this appears to manifest across three interrelated dimensions: the compression of time available for practitioner–client interaction, the expansion of administrative workload, and the resulting implications for the depth and quality of guidance practice.

5.1 Capacity pressures and time compression

The survey findings suggest that shorter appointment lengths sit within a broader pattern of time compression, rather than operating as an isolated feature of delivery. When considered alongside the appointment-volume data, this indicates that shortened sessions may reflect the number of interactions practitioners are expected to deliver within constrained working hours.

This pattern is consistent with wider evidence from adult services and higher education, where reduced appointment durations have similarly been associated with workload pressures, staffing constraints and increased demand. In this sense, shortened appointments appear to function as an adaptive response to capacity pressure: a way of maintaining access and throughput, but one that may reduce the time available for exploration, reflection and personalised guidance.

5.2 Administrative burden as a competing demand on time

In addition to direct delivery pressures, this study highlights the significant role of administrative demands and their influence on how practitioner time is allocated.

Survey responses indicate that:

- Documentation, action planning and reporting requirements consume a substantial proportion of practitioner time
- Administrative work frequently extends beyond scheduled hours, contributing to workload spillover

This aligns with evidence from adult employability services and Universal Credit implementation research, where administrative and process-driven requirements are shown to compete directly with time available for meaningful client interaction (Irvine et al., 2023; Dwyer et al., 2025). Importantly, this suggests that capacity constraints are not solely a

function of appointment volume, but also of how practitioner time is distributed between client-facing work and administrative / system requirements.

5.3 Implications for depth and quality of guidance

A consistent theme across both the survey findings and the wider literature reviewed is that guidance quality is time sensitive. This evidence suggests that shorter guidance interactions risk narrowing the scope of practice and limiting opportunities for exploration and personalised support (DfES, 2007; DWP, 2011a; Reid, 2022).

Evidence indicates an association between longer engagement durations and higher-quality interactions, while shorter interactions are more likely to be transactional or limited in scope. Similarly, Reid's (2022) research in higher education suggests that reduced appointment length can constrain the depth of exploration, reflection and personalised support that guidance is intended to provide.

This issue becomes particularly significant when considering learners with additional or overlapping risk factors. Recent DfE analysis shows that young people with EHCPs, persistent absence, low attainment and multiple risk factors face a substantially higher likelihood of becoming NEET, reinforcing the importance of holistic prevention approaches (Department for Education, 2026). In this context, shortened appointments and limited follow-up capacity may have acute implications for learners with more complex guidance needs, who may require more sustained and personalised support.

This is reflected in findings from the present study, where practitioners frequently linked time pressure to reduced opportunities for in-depth discussion and limitations on exploring individual needs. Respondents also described the delay or compression of follow-up work and communications, suggesting that capacity constraints affect not only the guidance interaction itself, but also the support surrounding it.

Taken collectively, the literature and survey findings support the interpretation that time is not simply a logistical constraint, but a core component of effective guidance practice.

5.4 Structural nature of capacity constraints

While individual factors such as time management or workflow efficiency may play a role, both the survey data and supporting literature suggest that capacity pressures are largely structural rather than individual. Respondents identified staffing levels, funding constraints and delivery expectations as underlying drivers of workload intensity and appointment compression. This aligns with wider policy analysis, which has similarly identified underfunding, fragmentation, limited/patchy access, as well as recruitment and retention pressures as features of the current career guidance system in England (Hooley, Percy and Neary, 2023).

In addition, findings from this study indicate that practitioner roles may be expanding beyond direct guidance delivery to include a wider range of responsibilities associated with careers programme implementation, as highlighted in Section 3. This expansion of role scope introduces additional competing priorities for practitioner time, further limiting the capacity available for one-to-one guidance.

This implies that capacity constraints are shaped not only by demand and resourcing, but also by how practitioner roles are structured and distributed across multiple functions. They are also shaped by the total volume of interactions practitioners are expected to deliver within a given timeframe, alongside the preparation, follow-up and administrative work attached to each interaction. However, the current evidence base, including this study, has limited visibility of these structural inputs in measurable terms, such as adviser-to-client ratios, administrative time allocation, or the proportion of time spent on non-guidance duties. This creates a gap between what practitioners experience and what is formally measured and understood at system level.

5.5 A measurement gap in understanding guidance delivery

A key implication emerging from the synthesis of findings is that critical aspects of guidance delivery are not consistently measured across the system. While outcomes such as progression, participation and satisfaction are often prioritised, there is comparatively little systematic data on:

- How much time practitioners have available
- How that time is allocated
- How delivery conditions vary across settings

This includes limited visibility of administrative workload, appointment length distribution and the extent to which practitioners are balancing multiple competing responsibilities. This measurement gap has important implications for the careers sector. Firstly, it limits understanding of the relationship between delivery conditions and outcomes. Secondly, it makes it harder to identify where capacity constraints are most acute and to design interventions that address underlying causes rather than the symptoms.

6. Implications and Recommendations

This section outlines implications and recommendations across three levels: practitioner, organisational and system.

6.1 Practitioner / Operational level

At the practitioner level, findings indicate that administrative workload and follow-up requirements are a significant contributor to perceived capacity pressure, often extending

beyond contracted working hours. There is therefore a need to protect practitioner time, particularly in relation to post-session documentation, action planning and record-keeping.

Where appropriate, practitioners may benefit from the adoption of improved digital tools, including AI-enabled systems, to support administrative processes such as drafting action plans, summarising session notes and structuring follow-up outputs. The potential value of such tools lies in their ability to reduce repetitive administrative workload, thereby helping to minimise spillover into evenings and weekends and allowing practitioners to maintain focus and presence during guidance interactions. However, practitioners and services should review carefully whether these tools genuinely reduce workload in practice and ensure that any use of AI-supported outputs remains subject to professional judgement, informed consent, data protection requirements and ethical safeguards, particularly when working with clients with complex needs.

Moreover, it is critical to emphasise that any efficiency gains achieved through technology should be used to protect practitioner capacity and wellbeing, rather than to increase the number of client appointments delivered. Alongside technological support, practitioners should be supported to maintain boundaries around workload and working hours, as well as prioritising depth and quality of interaction within the available timeframes.

Professional bodies, representative organisations and where relevant, trade unions may also have a role in supporting practitioners to articulate workload boundaries and advocate for sustainable delivery conditions.

6.2 Service / Organisational level

At the organisational level, capacity pressures appear to be shaped by a combination of staffing levels, delivery expectations, administrative requirements and role design. Reid (2022) suggests that reducing appointment lengths below commonly recommended durations risks undermining the depth and effectiveness of guidance practice. Therefore, services and institutions should review how guidance is structured and resourced in their setting, with particular attention to the following:

Appointment structures and delivery models

- Ensuring that full guidance sessions are not routinely replaced by shortened interactions
- Recognising that shorter appointments may have a legitimate role, particularly when used intentionally as part of a planned sequence of support, but should not be treated as a substitute for in-depth guidance where greater exploration or follow-up is required
- Monitoring the use of shortened appointments, including their frequency, rationale and distribution across learner groups, to ensure they are used intentionally rather than becoming an unexamined response to capacity pressure

- Ensuring that students with additional barriers or more complex transition needs, including those with SEND, EHCPs, persistent absence or multiple NEET risk factors, have access to additional guidance sessions and follow-up support where required

Administrative burden and workflow design

- Reducing duplication in data entry, reporting and tracking requirements
- Streamlining systems to improve efficiency and usability
- Ensuring that administrative expectations are proportionate to available practitioner time

Resourcing and role design

- Introducing or expanding administrative support roles where feasible
- Reviewing staffing models to ensure sufficient capacity for both delivery and follow-up
- Clarifying role expectations to avoid overextension across multiple functions, particularly where practitioners are expected to combine:
 - one-to-one guidance
 - programme coordination (e.g. work experience, events)
 - teaching or curriculum delivery

Where such responsibilities are combined, there is a risk that core guidance activity is compressed or deprioritised, even where appointment demand remains high.

Use of digital and AI-enabled systems

There is increasing potential for organisations to adopt and standardise digital tools, including AI-supported systems, to reduce administrative workload across their guidance services. At an organisational level, the effective use of such tools may improve the consistency and speed of documentation, reduce time spent on repetitive administrative tasks and support more sustainable workload distribution. However, implementation should be governed carefully, with clear expectations around appropriate use, data protection, consent and practitioner oversight. Technological efficiencies should not be used to justify increased caseloads, reduced appointment lengths or an increase in the number of clients seen per day.

Instead, the role of such tools should be to support existing professional practice, enhance sustainability of delivery and enable practitioners to dedicate the appropriate amount of time and care to each client interaction.

Evaluation of delivery models

Organisations may also benefit from treating changes to guidance delivery models as opportunities for structured evaluation or action research. Where services introduce changes such as shorter appointments, triage models, additional administrative support or AI-enabled documentation tools, they should monitor the effects on practitioner workload, appointment quality, follow-up capacity and learner experience. This would help ensure that changes are assessed not only in terms of throughput or efficiency, but also in relation to sustainability, equity and guidance quality.

6.3 System / Policy level

At a system level, the findings from this study, along with supporting evidence across secondary, adult and higher education contexts suggest that key dimensions of career guidance delivery remain insufficiently measured and therefore poorly understood. In particular, there is a lack of consistent data across the sector on appointment volume, length and distribution (e.g. proportion of sessions below recommended durations). We also lack consistent data and reporting on practitioner caseloads as well as the administrative time associated with guidance delivery.

This lack of visibility presents a structural challenge. Without clear and comparable measures of practitioner capacity, it is difficult to assess:

1. Whether services are operating within sustainable limits
2. The extent to which time constraints are shaping practice
3. How delivery conditions relate to outcomes

Improving measurement and system understanding

There is a strong case for developing clearer, standardised metrics across career guidance provision, particularly in relation to typical appointment length and variation in appointment duration by setting and need. Moreover, the monitoring of practitioner caseloads, appointment numbers per day and time spent on administrative tasks should be embedded alongside existing reporting frameworks.

At system level, this aligns with Milburn's (2026) concern that data on young people's journeys is fragmented across institutional silos, limiting the ability of services to understand transitions, identify unmet need and coordinate support. More consistent measurement could therefore:

- Provide a more accurate picture of delivery conditions
- Enable better comparison across settings
- Support more informed decision-making at policy and funding levels

In addition to measuring whether personal guidance has taken place, system-level monitoring should consider whether sufficient adviser time and follow-up capacity are available for students with additional barriers or multiple risk factors. This would help distinguish between baseline access to guidance and the capacity to provide support that is proportionate to need.

Future research and causal analysis

Beyond improved monitoring, there is also a need for larger-scale research capable of examining the relationship between delivery conditions and guidance outcomes more robustly. Future studies could test whether variables such as appointment length, appointment volume, caseload, administrative time and follow-up capacity are associated with differences in learner experience, career readiness, sustained destinations or other outcome measures. Where possible, longitudinal or quasi-experimental designs would help move the evidence base beyond descriptive association toward a stronger understanding of causal pathways.

Alignment between expectations and capacity

The findings also point to a misalignment between expected outcomes and service delivery models, as well as the resources available to practitioners. Where systems place increasing emphasis on outcomes (e.g. progression, career readiness, sustained destinations), without corresponding visibility of practitioner capacity, there is a risk that expectations become disconnected from what is operationally achievable.

As such, there is a need to ensure that expectations around guidance delivery are grounded in realistic assessments of capacity and that time is recognised as a core input to effective guidance, rather than an incidental variable.

Resourcing and structural considerations

While this study does not directly measure funding levels or staffing ratios, both the survey findings and wider research indicate that staffing levels, funding constraints and commissioning models are likely to play a significant role in shaping capacity and appointment structures. Therefore, future system-level work may benefit from greater integration of resource measures (e.g. staffing levels, funding per learner/client) alongside delivery measures (e.g. appointment time, contact frequency). This would support a more holistic understanding of how inputs, delivery conditions and outcomes interact with one another.

These issues may also warrant inclusion in larger national surveys or sector-level monitoring exercises, where more representative samples could help assess the prevalence, distribution and intensity of these pressures across settings.

7. Conclusion

This study set out to examine how current pressures on career guidance professionals are manifesting in practice, with particular attention to appointment volume and duration, administrative workload and capacity constraints. Across the findings, a consistent picture emerges. Career guidance delivery is increasingly shaped by limitations on practitioner time, with implications for how support is structured, experienced and sustained.

The analysis demonstrates that capacity pressures are not solely a function of appointment volume, but reflect a broader combination of factors, including shortened appointment structures, administrative workload, limited follow-up capacity and the expansion of practitioner roles across wider careers programme responsibilities. When considered alongside existing evidence from secondary, higher education and adult guidance contexts, these findings point to a shared pattern in which constrained capacity is associated with shorter interactions and a shift toward more transactional forms of support.

This matters because career guidance is not a peripheral activity. The wider evidence base demonstrates that career guidance can contribute to positive outcomes, but studies also show that the nature, length and quality of guidance interactions are important factors in determining its effectiveness. Furthermore, the findings from this study suggest that current evaluation approaches give insufficient visibility to the delivery inputs that make effective guidance possible, particularly practitioner time, administrative capacity and the ability to provide follow-up support.

The need for better visibility is especially important where learners face additional or overlapping barriers. If students with more complex transition needs require more sustained and personalised guidance, then measuring whether guidance has taken place is not sufficient. Access alone is not enough; the sector also needs visibility of whether guidance is resourced with sufficient time, capacity and follow-up support to accommodate learner need.

In conclusion, the findings suggest that a fuller understanding of career guidance effectiveness requires attention not only to outcomes, but also to the relationship between resources, practitioner activity, time-use and delivery conditions. This is becoming increasingly important as services explore technological solutions to productivity challenges and cost pressures. Greater attention to how guidance is delivered, alongside what it achieves, may provide a more complete lens for understanding and improving effectiveness across the sector.

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